

Chloride deregulation and GABA depolarization in MTOR related malformations of cortical development

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Abstract

Focal Cortical Dysplasia, Hemimegalencephaly and Cortical Tuber are pediatric epileptogenic malformations of cortical development (MCDs) frequently pharmaco-resistant and mostly surgically treated by the resection of epileptic cortex. Availability of cortical resection samples allowed significant mechanistic discoveries directly from human material. Causal brain somatic or germline mutations in the AKT/PI3K/DEPDC5/MTOR genes were identified. GABA_A mediated paradoxical depolarization, related to altered chloride (Cl⁻) homeostasis, was shown to participate to ictogenesis in human pediatric MCDs. However, the link between genomic alterations and neuronal hyperexcitability is still unclear. Here we studied the post translational interactions between the mTOR pathway and the regulation of cation-chloride cotransporters (CCC), KCC2 and NKCC1, that are largely responsible for controlling intracellular Cl⁻ and ultimately GABAergic transmission.

For this study, 35 children (25 MTORopathies and 10 pseudo controls, diagnosed by histology plus genetic profiling) were operated for drug resistant epilepsy. Postoperative cortical tissues were recorded on multielectrode array (MEA) to map epileptic activities. CCC expression level and phosphorylation status of the WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 pathway was measured during basal conditions and after pharmacological modulation. Direct interactions between mTOR and WNK1 pathway

1 components were investigated by immunoprecipitation. Membranous incorporation of MCD
2 samples in *Xenopus laevis* oocytes enabled Cl^- conductance and equilibrium potential (E_{GABA}) for
3 GABA measurement.

4 Of the 25 clinical cases, half harbored a somatic mutation in the mTOR pathway, while pS6
5 expression was increased in all MCD samples. Spontaneous interictal discharges were recorded in
6 65% of the slices. CCC expression was altered in MCDs, with a reduced KCC2/NKCC1 ratio and
7 decreased KCC2 membranous expression. CCC expression was regulated by the WNK1/SPAK-
8 OSR1 kinases through direct phosphorylation of Thr⁹⁰⁶ on KCC2, that was reversed by WNK1 and
9 SPAK antagonists (NEM and Staurosporine). mSIN1 subunit of MTORC2 was found to interact
10 with SPAK-OSR1 and WNK1. Interactions between these key epileptogenic pathways could be
11 reversed by the mTOR specific antagonist Rapamycin, leading to a dephosphorylation of CCCs
12 and recovery of the KCC2/NKCC1 ratio. The functional effect of such recovery was validated by
13 the restoration of the depolarizing shift in E_{GABA} by rapamycin, measured after incorporation of
14 MCD membranes to *X. laevis* oocytes, in line with a reestablishment of normal E_{Cl^-} .

15 Our study deciphers a protein interaction network through a phosphorylation cascade between
16 MTOR and WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 leading to chloride cotransporters deregulation, increased
17 neuronal chloride levels and GABA_A dysfunction in malformations of Cortical Development,
18 linking genomic defects and functional effects and paving the way to target epilepsy therapy.

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6 mTOR; rapamycin

7

8 **Introduction**

9 Focal Cortical Dysplasia (FCD) are a frequent etiology of focal drug resistant epilepsy requiring
10 surgical resections early in life to treat seizures. ^{1,2} Direct access to the epileptic cortex allowed its
11 early histological description 50 years ago, the tissue harboring “large bizarre neurons, grotesque
12 cells probably of glial origin, and a global appearance reminiscent yet distinct to tuberous
13 sclerosis”³. Further clinical characterization identified among these malformations of cortical
14 development a distinctive clinical presentation (early onset of seizures, pseudo continuous interictal
15 spikes on EEG, Cortical T2 hyperintensity along a trans mantle sign, PET hypometabolism)⁴⁻⁶,
16 associated with stereotyped histological abnormalities (loss of laminar and columnar organization,
17 cytomegalic neurons, balloon cells) classified as FCD type IIb.^{7,8} FCD type II was further
18 hallmarked by the discovery that a somatic mutation in the mTOR gene ((MTOR) c.7280T>C
19 (p.Leu2427Pro)) was causative of the cortical disorganization and epilepsy, as *in utero*
20 electroporation of the mutated mTOR in mouse embryos recapitulated key features of the human
21 disease. ⁹ This was later confirmed when larger cohorts identified both germline and single somatic
22 mutation of the MTOR pathway in Focal Cortical Dysplasia, Hemimegalencephaly (HMG) and
23 Cortical Tubers (TSC), including PI3K, AKT, DEPDC5, TSC1-2 genes mutations in >80% of the
24 samples, leading to a hyperactive MTOR pathway with high levels of expression of its downstream
25 effector phospho S6 (pS6). ¹⁰⁻¹³ Common mechanisms may therefore underly epileptogenesis in
26 different histological entities grouped as mTORopathies, or MTOR related Malformations of
27 Cortical Development (MCDs). Deciphering how these mutations translate into neuronal
28 hyperexcitability and clinical seizures is however hampered by the low level of Variant Allele
29 Frequency (<5%) in the case of somatic mutations and by the role of MTOR as a critical hub in

1 many cellular signaling pathways (autophagy, protein synthesis, cell survival).^{13,14} At the
2 transcriptional level, AKT mutation can lead through FOXG1 transcription factor to Reelin
3 derepression and paracrine Reelin secretion causing neuronal altered migration.¹⁵ MTOR related
4 RNA translational deregulation increases the expression of IRSp53, CREB 1 and ADK that are
5 associated with epileptic seizures.¹⁶ These molecular studies do not still account definitively for
6 the mechanisms underlying seizures in the dysplastic cortex, where imbalance between inhibitory
7 and excitatory networks sustains epileptic activity.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ GABAergic transmission is particularly
8 deregulated in FCD, with a global reduction of the number of interneurons, that cluster around
9 cytomegalic cells at the grey-white matter junction.^{20,21} GABA_A neurotransmission has been
10 shown to be positively involved in seizure initiation in *in vitro* preparations of human MCD cortical
11 slices²² and is associated with a GABA_A dependent pacemaker activity of dystrophic and
12 cytomegalic neurons.²³⁻²⁵ This paradoxical GABAergic depolarization may be explained by
13 neuronal chloride accumulation leading to a shift in its reversal potential due to altered expression
14 of chloride neuronal cotransporters. Specifically, decreased levels of the membrane chloride
15 extruder KCC2 (SLC12A5) and abnormal expression of the chloride intruder NKCC1(SLC12A2)
16 were observed in various FCD subtypes.²⁶⁻³² The expression of NKCC1 and KCC2 is regulated
17 partially through post translational phosphorylation cascades associated with the WNK1-SPAK-
18 OSR1 pathway: WNK1 activates the kinases SPAK and OSR1 which directly phosphorylate and
19 stimulate the expression of chloride intruder NKCC1, while inhibiting the expression of chloride
20 extruder KCC2 through declustering and endocytosis.^{33,34} Interestingly, the WNK pathway is
21 regulated upstream by the PI3/AKT/mTOR pathway, as AKT directly phosphorylates WNK1,
22 indirectly activates WNK3-WNK4 and mTORC2 directly phosphorylates OSR1.^{35,36} The link
23 between the mTOR mutations and epileptogenicity have been mainly addressed from an
24 architectural point of view, with defective neuronal migration and dysmorphogenesis,^{15,37} but the
25 link between genetic alterations and GABA_A dependent epileptogenesis remains to be addressed.

26 Here we postulate that mTOR pathway mutation can deregulate chloride cotransporter at a post
27 translational level, leading to a shift in reversal potential E_{Cl^-} , and paradoxical GABA_A induced
28 depolarization in MCD. To address this, we performed *ex vivo* electrophysiology and biochemistry
29 studies on human cortical slices from FCD, HMG and TSC, grouped as MTOR related
30 Malformations of Cortical Development. We report direct interactions between mTOR and

1 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 / NKCC1/KCC2, that sustain GABAergic mediated hyperexcitability in
2 MCDs, and could be targeted pharmacologically to treat seizures.

3

4 **Material and methods**

5 **Patients and study design**

6 Patients' parents or legal guardians gave informed written consent for the storage, and research on
7 biological specimens provided as part of treatment. The biological collection stored in our
8 institution and the study are declared respectively under n° D2009-955, and n° ANR 20- CE17-
9 003.

10 Brain cortical samples were obtained from children undergoing epilepsy surgery between March
11 2021 and June 2023. A comprehensive presurgical evaluation was performed with EEG-video
12 monitoring, 3T MRI read by an experienced neuro radiologist, neuropsychological evaluation,
13 genetic testing, and when required 18FDG-PET or intracranial EEG recordings with depth
14 electrodes (SEEG). The surgery was not modified for the study and consisted in “en bloc
15 resections” to avoid excessive manipulations of the tissue as previously reported.³²

16 We included patients operated for mTOR related malformations of cortical development and a
17 “pseudo control” group of epileptic children in whom cortical samples were taken around a brain
18 lesion (peritumoral cortex, peri stroke, Rasmussen). Histological examination confirmed the
19 absence of tumor or mTOR related histological abnormalities in the pseudo-controls.

20 **In vitro electrophysiology recordings and analysis**

21 Brains samples were immediately placed in iced sucrose artificial Cerebro Spinal Fluid (aACSF)
22 and transferred to the lab, where meninges and blood vessels were gently removed to allow slicing
23 with a vibratome. ³⁸ aACSF consisted of (in millimolar): 124 NaCl, 3 KCl, 26 NaHCO₃, 1.6 CaCl₂,
24 1.3 MgCl₂, and 10 D-glucose, at pH 7.4. After storage in an interface chamber with continuous
25 oxygenated aACSF perfusion at 37°C for 1 hour, 400 μm thick cortical slices were then recorded
26 in a 12x10 Multi-electrode array (MEA, MultiChannel Systems) bathed with oxygenated aACSF
27 at 37° C to record spontaneous cortical activity as previously described. ^{32,39,40} Pharmacological
28 studies on spontaneous interictal discharges (IID) were performed in modified aACSF containing

1 N EthylMalmeide (0.5 mM) and Staurosporine (8 μ M) to block WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 kinases, BYL
2 719 (10 μ M), Everolimus (1 μ M) and Rapamycine (0.1-0.5 μ M) to block PI3K/AKT/MTOR
3 pathway.

4 Local field potentials (LFPs) were then analyzed (amplitude, width, frequency) with Clampfit
5 software (pClamp Software; Molecular Devices), using visual analysis and the automated event
6 detector toolbox via threshold detection to quantify IID on active electrodes under physiological
7 and pharmacological conditions. We further performed time-frequency power spectrum analysis of
8 the MEA signal. Raw data was offline pre-processed using in-house developed software and
9 MATLAB code, as follows: (i) DC removal, (ii) low-pass filter (cut-off frequency: 200 Hz), (iii)
10 signal down-sampling (subsampling rate of 1:20, down-sample from a sampling frequency of
11 10000 samples/s to 500 samples/s), (iv) visual inspection for possible noisy electrode rejection.
12 Time-frequency analysis was computed using fractional adaptive superlets (FASLT), a super-
13 resolution method providing sharp representations across the whole frequency domain based on a
14 set of wavelets ($c_l = 3$; $o = [1..7]$).^{41,42} Fieldtrip and in-house Matlab code was used to illustrate
15 epileptogenic activity power topographic distribution across the slice.⁴³ For measuring the effect
16 of drug application, power averages per electrode across the whole time-frequency spectrum were
17 computed for the active electrodes (electrodes with the most pronounced epileptogenic activity)
18 and represented as heatmaps over the MEA array.

19 **Biochemistry studies**

20 **Expression analysis**

21 Membranes were prepared as previously described.⁴⁴ Briefly the cortex sample was homogenized
22 in a Polytron system in 10 volumes of an ice-cold buffer containing 50 mM Tris pH 7.4, 0.32 M
23 sucrose, 5 mM EDTA and 1 mM EGTA supplemented with complete protease inhibitor (Roche).
24 The homogenate was centrifuged at 800-1000 g for 10 min (4°C). The supernatant was collected
25 and centrifuged at 100 000 g for 45 min (4°C). The pellet (P2) was osmotically shocked in 10
26 volumes of ice-cold water. The microsome suspension was centrifuged at 100,000g for 45 min
27 (4°C). The remaining pellet (P3) was suspended in a buffer containing 10 mM Hepes (pH 7.4) and
28 10 mM KCl and then centrifuged again at 100 000g for 45 min (4°C). The last pellet (P4) was
29 stored at -80°C until use. Protein concentrations were tested using a BCA Protein Assay Kit.

1 Lysates (20 to 30 μ g) were separated by 8 % sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) polyacrylamide gel
2 electrophoresis and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane. The membranes were then
3 immunoblotted in 5% (w/v) non-fat powdered milk in TPBS with the indicated primary antibodies
4 overnight at 4°C. The blots were then washed three times with TPBS and incubated for 1 hour at
5 room temperature with secondary HRP-conjugated antibodies diluted 5000-fold. GAPDH was used
6 as an internal control. After repeating the washing steps, the signal was detected using an ECL
7 reagent. Immunoblots were developed using ChemiDoc™ Imaging Systems (Bio-Rad,
8 Feldkirchen). Densities of bands were measured with ImageJ.⁴⁵

9 **Co-immunoprecipitation Assays**

10 Co-immunoprecipitation was performed to detect the physical interaction between mTORC2 and
11 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 by using the Immunoprecipitation Kit dynabeads protein G. Briefly, samples
12 were homogenized using a Polytron system in ice-cold buffer. The homogenate was first
13 centrifuged at a low speed of 800-1000g for 10 min to remove all debris. The supernatant is then
14 centrifuged at 14500g for 30 min. Immunoprecipitation of the antigens was achieved by a 60 min
15 rotating incubation at room temperature (RT) of the resulting supernatant with 2 μ g of anti-WNK1
16 Ab or anti-mSIN1 Ab. IgG Ab was used as a negative control followed by the addition of Protein
17 G-conjugated magnetic beads for 60 min. The magnetic beads were washed 3 times before elution
18 in Laemmli sample buffer. Proteins were resolved by SDS-PAGE and transferred to nitrocellulose
19 membranes for Western blot analysis. Anti-mTOR Ab and anti-SPAK/OSR1 Ab diluted to 1:1000
20 were applied overnight at 4°C. The bound proteins were detected using Goat anti-rabbit diluted to
21 1:5000 coupled to horseradish peroxidase HRP.

22 For phospho-antibody immunoprecipitation experiment, total KCC2 and total NKCC1 were
23 immunoprecipitated from indicated tissue extracts ⁴⁶. This was incubated with 4 μ g of the indicated
24 KCC2, NKCC1 antibody or 4 μ g mouse IgG, conjugated to 15 μ l of Protein G–Sepharose.
25 Incubation was for overnight at 4°C with gentle agitation. The immuno-precipitates were then
26 washed three times with lysis buffer to be finally eluted with the sample buffer. KCC2pThr⁹⁰⁶ or
27 NKCC1 pThr^{203,207,212} antibody was detected via western blot. The bound proteins were detected
28 by using a Rabbit anti-sheep IgG coupled horseradishperoxidase HRP.

1 **KCC2 biotinylation**

2 Slices were treated with the drugs for 30 min with 95%O₂/5%CO₂ aACSF. Surface proteins were
3 labeled with 1.0 mg/ml sulfo-NHS-SS-biotin in ice-cold aACSF, for 45 min, at 4°C, with bubbling
4 95%O₂/5%CO₂. Following biotinylation, slices were washed three times in ice-cold aACSF, and
5 then lysed in lysis buffer. Cellular debris were removed by centrifugation at 18,000 g, for 20 min,
6 at 4°C and protein concentrations were determined using the BCA protein assay. 100µl of
7 streptavidine were added to 600µg of proteins lysate followed by rotating incubation overnight at
8 4°C. Beads were pulled down after each wash by gentle centrifugation. The proteins were eluted
9 with 2XSDS reducing buffer and heated at 85°C. Western blotting was performed using an anti-
10 KCC2 antibody.

11 **Histology**

12 Part of the cortical samples used for electrophysiological experiments were subjected to
13 histological examination by experimented neuropathologists to ensure that the cortices used in
14 MEA recordings were indeed pathological and they were considered as “mirror block”. Samples
15 presenting abnormal cortical cytoarchitecture, dysmorphic neurons with or without balloon cells
16 were considered representative of the epileptogenic lesion and included in further
17 immunohistochemical study. Histological diagnosis was performed on 3-µm-thick slices stained
18 with Hematoxylin-Phloxine-Saphran (HPS), using the 3 following criteria: abnormal cortical
19 architecture, dysmorphic neurons and balloon cells as defined by the 2022 ILAE consensus
20 classification of focal cortical dysplasia.⁴⁷ Unstained 3-µm-thick slices of formalin-fixed, paraffin-
21 embedded (FFPE) tissues were submitted for immunostaining using an automated Stainer (Dako
22 Omnis, Glostrup, Denmark). The following primary antibodies were used: KCC2 (1 :1000,
23 Rabbit), phosphoS6 (1:400). In 3 patients (n = 9 slices), ½ cortical slices were treated with
24 rapamycin before fixation. HPS and immunohistochemistry slides were digitized using an Aperio
25 AT2 slide scanner (Leica, Nussloch, Germany). Digital slides were then viewed using the IDS7
26 application (Sectra, Norway). Cell count was performed manually by repurposing the IDS7 mitotic
27 counting tool, after a 1 mm² cortical region of interest (ROI) was chosen as representative of the
28 sample. The total number of neurons (normal and dysmorphic) / mm² was measured, along the
29 number of neurons with cytoplasmic (IC) or membranous (MB) KCC2 immunostaining.

1 Comparison of total, IC, MB KCC2 was done: (i) between controls, and mTOR mutated tissue
2 (including, FCD, TSC, HMG cases); (ii) before and after treatment by rapamycin.

3 **Immunofluorescence assay**

4 FFPE sections (5- μ m) were deparaffinated in xylene and antigen retrieval was performed using a
5 pH 9.0 buffer (Akoya Biosciences, USA). After permeabilization in PBS 0,1% BSA 0,2% Triton-
6 X and blocking in PBS 3% BSA for 1h, the slides were incubated overnight at 4°C in blocking
7 buffer containing the primary antibodies: NeuN (1:150, Merck ABN90), pS6 (1:100, Cell Signaling
8 Technology 2211) and KCC2 (1:50, DSHB N1/12). Secondary antibodies (1:400, Alexafluor 488
9 goat anti-mouse, Alexafluor 568 goat anti-rabbit and Alexafluor 647 goat anti-guinea pig) were
10 incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. DAPI (1:1000, Invitrogen D3571) was used as
11 nuclear stain and the slides were mounted using Immu-Mount (Eprelia 9990402). Images were
12 captured at 63x with Spinning Disk Zeiss system (Intelligent Imaging Innovations, USA), an
13 Examiner.Z1 upright stand (Carl Zeiss, Germany), a CSU-W1 head (Yokogawa, Japan), and an
14 ORCA-Flash 4.0 camera (Hamamatsu, Japan). The same parameters were applied to all images
15 during capturing and processing (ImageJ).

16 **Molecular Diagnosis**

17 DNA extracted from FFPE or frozen cortical samples was analyzed by targeted Next-Generation
18 Sequencing (NGS) of 36 genes (Suppl Data) mainly involved in the mTOR signaling pathway.
19 Briefly, all coding exons of selected genes were screened by paired-end sequencing reactions of
20 150-bp reads on a MiSeq platform (Illumina, Paris, France) after capture-based target enrichment.
21 The bioinformatic analysis included the trimming of raw NGS reads (FASTQ), mapping, variant
22 calling, variant annotation, and filtering. Somatic variant curation was performed as recommended
23 in cancer.⁴⁸

24 **Micro transplantation of GABA Receptors from MCD cortical samples to X.** 25 **laevis**

26 Membranes from MCD cortical samples were prepared and injected into oocytes as previously
27 reported.⁴⁹ Briefly, 0.5 g of previously frozen tissue was homogenized in 50mM Tris pH 7.4, 300
28 mM sucrose, 1mM EGTA and 5mM EDTA. The filtrate was centrifuged for 10 min at 1000 g twice.

1 The supernatant was then centrifuged for 1 h at 100 000 g. The membranes were suspended in
2 water and kept frozen at -80°C until used for an experiment.

3 *Xenopus laevis* oocytes were obtained from the IBENS (Paris, France) Xenopus facility (husbandry
4 authorization #D75-05-31; project authorization Apafis #28867-2020121814485893), as well as
5 from TEFOR (Paris Saclay, France). They were prepared as previously described⁵⁰. Briefly small
6 pieces of ovary were gently shaken at room temperature for 2–3 h in a Ca²⁺-free ND96 (96 mM
7 NaCl, 2 mM KCl, 1mM MgCl₂ and 5 mM HEPES) at pH 7.4 solution supplemented with
8 collagenase 1A. After adding CaCl₂ (1.8 mM) and carefully washing off the enzyme, defolliculated
9 and healthy-looking stage V-VI oocytes were selected and allowed to recover for a few hours (up
10 to 24 h) before the injection.⁵¹ The next day, each membrane preparation was injected into oocytes
11 at a protein concentration of 2-5 mg.ml⁻¹ (50 nl volume). Membranes were always microinjected
12 into the animal pole of the *X. laevis* oocyte near the equatorial band.⁴⁹ The injected oocytes were
13 incubated at 17 °C for 24–48 h in ND96 (96 mM NaCl, 2 mM KCl, 1.8 mM CaCl₂, 1mM MgCl₂
14 and 5 mM HEPES) at pH 7.4 for electrophysiological studies. The incubation media were
15 supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin (100 units/100 µg ml⁻¹). Two-electrodes voltage-clamp
16 experiments were performed using a TEV-200A amplifier (Dagan, Minneapolis, MN), 1 or 2 days
17 after micro-transplantation co-injection. Oocytes were subsequently placed in a microchamber and
18 superfused with ND96 (pH 7.4) while being punctured with two low-resistance (0.5–2.0-
19 megaohm), 3M KCl-filled microelectrodes. Currents were recorded in response to a voltage
20 protocol consisting of 20 mV steps from -80 to +80 mV during 800 ms. The reversal potential of
21 the GABA receptor was determined using solutions containing ND96 alone, ND96 + 250µM
22 GABA or ND96 + 250µM GABA + 0,5µM Rapamycin. Whole cell currents were recorded at the
23 holding potential V_H = - 50 mV. The chloride reversal potential (E_{Cl⁻}) was determined by I/V
24 relationship while using a solution with low Cl⁻ concentration (10mM NaCl). Chloride was replaced
25 by gluconate, and calcium was raised to 3 mM (to compensate for Ca²⁺ chelation by gluconate salt).
26 The data were filtered at 500 Hz, digitized using a digidata 1440A analog-to-digital converter and
27 analyzed using Axon pClamp 10 software (Molecular Devices).

28 **Statistics and reproducibility**

29 Results are expressed as means +/- SE or +/- SD. Statistical analysis was performed using Sigma
30 Plot version 11.0. Western blot data were analyzed for statistical significance using the two-tailed

1 t Student's test. Electrophysiological experiments were studied with non-parametric Kruskal–
2 Wallis and Wilcoxon test was used for repeated measurement on a single sample. P values < 0.05
3 were considered significant.

4 For time frequency analyses, normality assumption analyses (Shapiro-Wilk Test) have been
5 performed, followed by parametrical tests (ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD/Tukey Kramer tests
6 and t tests with Bonferroni correction where required).

7 n is the number of western blots, slices or oocytes, and N is number of patients or frogs.

8

9 **Results**

10 **Cohort, histology, and molecular diagnosis**

11 35 children were included in this study (Table, Suppl Data), with 25 somatic mTOR related
12 malformations of cortical development and 10 pseudo control cases. In the mTOR group, M/F ratio
13 was 1.7 with a mean age at surgery of 6.2 years (range 0.5-18.8 y, sd 5.5y). Focal resection was
14 performed in 15 cases, and lobar or multilobar/hemispheric disconnection was done in $n=3$ and 7
15 respectively. The samples were mostly taken in the frontal lobe ($n=10$) and central region ($n=6$).
16 Histology was as follows: Focal Cortical Dysplasia Type II (FCD II) (a $N=8$; b $N=6$),
17 Hemimegalencephaly (HMG) ($N = 6$) or Tuber (TSC) ($N = 5$). The “pseudo control” group
18 consisted of 10 epileptic children (4 male, mean age 8.2 y, sd 3.3y). The samples originated mainly
19 from the central region (in 5 cases of hemispherotomy) and diagnosis was as follows: Peri lesional
20 Cortex (Tumor $N=3$, vascular malformation $N=2$), Rasmussen's encephalopathy ($N=3$) and stroke
21 ($N=2$).

22 A strong intracytoplasmic pS6 immunostaining was observed in cytomegalic cells (dysmorphic
23 neurons and balloon cells) in all representative samples, confirming the activation of the mTOR
24 pathway (Fig 2A), that was further quantified with western blot as expression of pS6 was
25 significantly higher ($n = 5WB$, $P = 0.008$) in MCDs cortex ($N = 2 : 1FCDII$ and 1 TSC; $1.02 \pm$
26 0.02) than in pseudo control cortex $N = 3$ (Stroke / Rasmussen / Peritumoral Cortex; 0.52 ± 0.08).

27 NGS identified a single somatic mutation in 48% (10/21) patients with available tissue material.
28 Fifty percent (5/10) of the patients exhibited gain-of-function mutation in *PIK3CA* (2 HMG, 2

1 *tuber;1FCDIIA*) except for one case of disruption, and 30% (3/10) had activating missense
2 mutations in *MTOR* (*1FCDIIa*, *1FCDIIb*, *1HMG*). NGS also detected a somatic missense
3 mutation in *TSC2* ($n=1$) and a loss-of-function mutation in *SMAD4* ($n=1$, FCDIIb) (Fig 2B and
4 Table). Mutational variant allelic frequency ranged from 1 to 14% (median: 2%). Interestingly, all
5 *PIK3CA* mutations were found in patients under 4 years of age. In addition, germline mutations in
6 *TSC2* were observed in all patients with TSC ($N=5$), including one case with additional germline
7 mutation in *PKD1*. (Fig 2B).

9 **MCD cortical slices display spontaneous epileptic events *in vitro* and** 10 **altered CCC expression**

11 57 slices from 17 patients (6FCDIIa, 4FCDIIb, 4 TSC and 3HMG) were recorded on MEAs
12 (median = 3 slices/patient). Spontaneous IIDs were recorded in 37 slices (65%) in physiological
13 aACSF with a mean frequency of 1.56 ± 1.19 Hz, a mean amplitude of 80.12 ± 32.52 μ V, and a
14 mean duration of 29.65 ± 16.02 ms (Fig 2C). The mean cortical area displaying IID was $16.85 \pm$
15 5.99 mm² corresponding to $9.36 \pm 3.33\%$ of the cortex explored. These data are consistent with
16 our previous reports ³².

17 Western blot analysis showed an inversion of the KCC2/NKCC1 ratio in MCD tissue as compared
18 to control tissue ($n = 9$ western blots; $N = 6$ MCDs: 2FCD, 2TSC and 2HMG, $N = 3$ controls:
19 Stroke / Rasmussen / Peritumoral Cortex). Mean expression of NKCC1 was 1.253 ± 0.072 in
20 MCDs vs 0.674 ± 0.054 for controls ($P < 0.001$), while values for KCC2 were 0.199 ± 0.032 in MCD
21 vs 1.281 ± 0.070 for Ctrl ($P < 0.001$). KCC2/NKCC1 ratio was 1.253 ± 0.072 in MCD vs $0.674 \pm$
22 0.054 in controls ($P < 0.001$) (Fig 2D).

23 Immunohistochemistry displayed an intracytoplasmic localization of KCC2 in dysmorphic neurons
24 compared to the controls (fig 2E): membranous expression of KCC2 was reduced in the MTOR
25 group as compared to the control group with a membrane/ intracellular ratio of 2.01 ± 3.03 and 6.5
26 ± 14.6 respectively ($P = 0.0001$) with $n = 9$ slices and $N = 3$ patients.

27

1 Chloride cotransporter expression is regulated by WNK1/SPAK- 2 OSR1 Kinases

3 To study the regulation of cation chloride cotransporters NKCC1/KCC2 by the WNK1/SPAK-
4 OSR1 kinases, we used NEM and Staurosporine that dephosphorylate the T loop and S loop
5 phosphorylation sites Thr²³³ and Ser³⁷³ of SPAK respectively. ⁵² (Fig3)

6 First, we confirmed that treatment with NEM and Staurosporine reduced the overall level of
7 phosphorylated SPAK/OSR1 (Fig 3A) as the SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³/total SPAK-OSR1 ratio was lower
8 in NEM (0.494 ± 0.025) and Staurosporine (0.415 ± 0.025) conditions than in control (DMSO)
9 (1.036 ± 0.016; *p*<0.001, *n* = 4 western blots and *N* = 3 MCD patients (2FCD and 1HMG). Then
10 we quantified KCC2 and NKCC1 expression under control, NEM and Staurosporine and found a
11 slight, yet non-significant decrease in NKCC1 (0.892 ± 0.114 vs 1.132 ± 0.125; *P* = 0.188 under
12 NEM and 0.895 ± 0.139 vs 1.132 ± 0.125; *P* = 0.236 under Staurosporine) and a significant increase
13 in KCC2 expression (1.118 ± 0.208 vs 0.661 ± 0.126; *P* = 0.024 under NEM and 1.284 ± 0.231 vs
14 0.661 ± 0.126; *P* = 0.014 under Staurosporine), resulting in the restoration of the KCC2/NKCC1
15 ratio (0.971 ± 0.077 vs 0.547 ± 0.092; *P* = 0.005 under NEM and 1.447 ± 0.252 vs 0.547 ± 0.092;
16 *P* = 0.007 under Staurosporine) *n* = 6 WB and *N* = 4 MCD cortices (Fig 3B).

17 Interestingly, restoration of the cation chloride cotransporters expression resulted in suppression of
18 the interictal epileptic activity (Fig 3C) on MEA recordings (*n*=5). Indeed, IID were stopped in 3
19 slices after a mean delay of 30 minutes of bathing aACSF with N EthylMalmeide (0.5 mM). In the
20 remaining 2 cases, mean IID frequency and amplitude reduced from 1.932 ± 0.594 Hz to 1.669
21 ± 0.726 and 55.228 ± 27.159 to 13.106 ± 9.699μV respectively.

23 MTOR interacts with WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 Kinases

24 To analyze putative physical interactions between mTOR protein and WNK1/SPAK-OSR1, we
25 performed co-immunoprecipitations experiments in the MCD cortical lysates using antibodies
26 directed against mTOR, and mSIN1 subunit of mTORC2. The precipitate was further analyzed
27 with antibodies against WNK1 and SPAK/OSR1. Our result revealed that endogenous mTOR and
28 mSIN1 interact with WNK1 and SPAK/OSR1 (Fig 4A). The binding interaction between SPAK/
29 OSR1 and mSIN1 appears to be dependent on the activation status of the two kinases, as application

1 of WNK inhibitor WNK463 or rapamycin caused a reduced immunoprecipitation of WNK1 with
2 mSIN1 ($n = 2$ and $N = 2$ MCD: 1FCD and 1 HMG for each condition). Under control condition
3 where normal purified IgG was used for IP, we saw no detectable endogenous co-
4 immunoprecipitation of the two proteins. In support of a functional interaction between mTOR and
5 SPAK/OSR1, we found a decrease in the phosphorylation level of SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³ when we
6 treated the cortical samples with inhibitors of the PI3K/AKT/MTOR pathway BYL 719 ($0.74 \pm$
7 0.02), Everolimus (0.75 ± 0.02) or rapamycin (0.60 ± 0.04) vs 1.05 ± 0.02 in DMSO ($n = 4$ and N
8 $= 4$ patients; $P < 0.001$) (Fig 4B).

10 **MTOR inhibition restores KCC2 membrane insertion**

11 To analyze the functional interactions between MTOR protein network and cation chloride co
12 transporters, we studied the phosphorylation levels of NKCC1 and KCC2 while inhibiting the
13 mTOR pathway. To do this, we performed immunoprecipitation after treatment with BYL719,
14 Everolimus and Rapamycin using specific antibodies for KCC2pThr⁹⁰⁶ and NKCC1 pThr^{203,207,212}
15 to precipitate KCC2 and NKCC1 (Fig 4B). The ratio of KCC2pThr⁹⁰⁶ to total KCC2 ($n = 6$ western
16 blot and $N = 4$ MCD : 2 FCD, 1 TSC and 1 HMG) was significantly decreased in the lysate
17 following treatment with BYL719 (1.12 ± 0.04 vs 0.90 ± 0.08 , $P = 0.026$), Everolimus (1.12 ± 0.04
18 vs 0.77 ± 0.09 vs, $P < 0.001$) and Rapamycin (1.12 ± 0.04 vs 0.64 ± 0.06 , $P < 0.001$) respectively
19 compared to untreated (Fig4B). Both Everolimus (0.33 ± 0.06 vs 0.57 ± 0.04 , $p = 0.002$) and
20 Rapamycin (0.28 ± 0.07 vs 0.57 ± 0.04 , $P = 0.002$) reduced the phosphorylation ratio of NKCC1
21 pThr^{203,207,212} compared to total NKCC1, while BYL719 did not modify the dephosphorylation of
22 NKCC1 pThr^{203,207,212} (0.55 ± 0.11 vs 0.57 ± 0.04) relative to total NKCC1, $P = 1$) (Fig4B) with n
23 $= 4$ western blot and $N = 4$ MCD patients (2FCD, 1TSC and 1HMG).

24 As phosphorylation of KCC2 is related to its degree of internalization, we then performed
25 biotinylation assay to quantify membranous, total, and cytosolic KCC2 expression (Fig 5).
26 Quantitative analysis (fig5A) revealed no significant difference in total KCC2 expression between
27 non treated and Rapamycin lysates (KCC2/GADPH ratio: 0.99 ± 0.1 vs 0.92 ± 0.06 ; $P = 0.56$). On
28 the other hand, rapamycin decreased the intracellular fraction of KCC2 as compared to DMSO
29 (0.73 ± 0.05 vs 1.12 ± 0.08 , $P = 0.002$). along with an increase in the membranous expression of
30 KCC2 (KCC2/GAPDH ratio: 1.1861 ± 0.15 vs 0.63 ± 0.12 , $P = 0.002$). This suggests that

1 rapamycin rescues the expression of KCC2 at the membrane, through dephosphorylation of KCC2
2 Thr⁹⁰⁶. Indeed, immunofluorescence analysis in MCD cortical samples treated with rapamycin
3 confirms its dramatic effect on the membrane inclusion of KCC2. While non-treated MCD neurons
4 are characterized by a uniformly distributed cytoplasmic signal of the anti-KCC2 antibody (Fig
5 5B), thirty minutes of rapamycin treatment was sufficient to drive the bulk of KCC2 to the
6 membrane and to clear the cytoplasmic signal (Fig 5C).

7

8 **MTOR inhibition restores E_{GABA} and has an antiepileptic effect**

9 To test whether the effect of rapamycin on the KCC2 reinsertion into the membrane has a direct
10 effect on the regulation of intracellular chloride content, assessed by E_{GABA} , we used the oocyte
11 heterologous testing system. Previous research has shown that membrane extracts from human
12 epileptic brains are associated with a depolarizing shift in the GABA reversal potential when
13 injected into oocytes and linked to a different ratio of membranous NKCC1 / KCC2 in epileptic vs
14 control membrane preparations.^{51,53} We therefore investigated whether rapamycin treatment could
15 influence GABA_A induced currents of MCD membrane-injected oocytes. Oocytes injected with
16 MCD membranes, but not control water-injected oocytes, responded to GABA exposure with an
17 inward current (-12.93 ± 1.91 nA $n = 15$ oocytes $N = 3$ *Xenopus* and $N = 3$ patients: 2FCD an
18 1HMG) (Fig 6A). The reversal potential calculated from the current-voltage relation was $-16.28 \pm$
19 0.59 mV, similar to the previously reported value (-18.5 ± 0.2 mV)⁵². The values of chloride
20 reversal potential E_{Cl^-} in the MCD oocytes was determined by IV curves while using a low chloride
21 (10mM NaCl) exposition. Mean E_{Cl^-} was -24.44 ± 1.68 mV ($n = 10$ MCD oocytes), which is
22 comparable to E_{Cl^-} (Cl⁻ equilibrium potential in *Xenopus* oocytes) in native noninjected oocyte.⁵³
23 Treatment of the injected oocytes with rapamycin (0.5 μ M) was able to significantly shift E_{GABA} to
24 a more negative potential (-29.5 ± 10.24 mV $n = 14$ oocytes; $N = 3$ frogs and $N = 3$ MCD patients),
25 in line with the predicted effect of rapamycin on KCC2 membrane reinsertion (Fig 6B). Under our
26 conditions, E_{GABA} in MCD injected oocytes is close to the E_{Cl^-} in *Xenopus* oocytes. This suggests
27 that the shift of E_{GABA} towards positive potentials is not the consequence of a change in chloride
28 transmembrane gradient of the whole oocyte but is related to functional imbalance of NKCC1 and
29 KCC2 in MCDs

1 To determine the functional consequence of restored KCC2 expression by rapamycin treatment on
2 the epileptic activity, we performed MEA recordings on the treated human MCD cortical slices.
3 We found that bathing the aACSF solution with rapamycin blocked interictal epileptic activity in
4 7 slices after a mean delay of 15 min (Fig 6C). Removal of the rapamycin restored interictal activity
5 in these slices, thus confirming that MTOR inhibition with rapamycin has an antiepileptic effect
6 on human cortical MCD slices *ex vivo*.

7 Rapamycin's functional effect was also assessed with spectral analyses of the MEA signal.
8 Heatmaps of average power for individual slices revealed a suppression effect of rapamycin on the
9 power spectrum both in the low (0.6 – 2Hz, Suppl Figure) and high (2 – 40Hz, Fig. 6D, E, F)
10 frequency ranges compared to aACSF. We observed a pattern of rhythmic bursts, potentially
11 involved in epileptic activity spreading which was significantly reduced by rapamycin treatment
12 (power $M = 1.87$, $SD = 0.22$ vs. aACSF, $M = 2.15$, $SD = 0.19$, $t(2.66) = 14$, $P = 0.01$, $d = 1.33$).
13 Removal of rapamycin reverted this effect (aACSF vs. Washed, $p = 0.96$), in line with the
14 observations on ictal activity.

15

16 Discussion

17 Here, using electrophysiology, biochemistry, and pharmacological modulation *ex vivo* in human
18 focal cortical dysplasia type II, HMG and TSC, we show physical interactions between mTOR and
19 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 kinases leading to the phosphorylation of the chloride cotransporters
20 NKCC1/KCC2, resulting in a depolarizing shift of E_{Cl^-} and ultimately hyperexcitability and
21 epilepsy.

22 Chloride co transporter expression is a key regulator of neuronal excitability through cerebral
23 development; high levels of NKCC1 during embryonic life leads to increased neuronal chloride
24 and GABA depolarization, while progressive expression of KCC2 after birth in human shifts E_{Cl^-}
25 negatively, and GABA becomes inhibitory in a caudal-rostral progression.⁵⁵ Interestingly,
26 embryonic like expression of chloride cotransporters was reported in human MCDs. Increased
27 expression of NKCC1 was noted on both astrocytes and neurons from MCD,²⁷ whereas a global
28 neuronal decreased expression of KCC2 was displayed along abnormalities of its cell localization
29 with rare membranous and important cytosolic immunoreactivity.^{28,30} However, if these results

1 suggest either a default in membrane addressing or an excess in endocytosis, chloride cotransporter
2 deregulation in MCDs has not yet been deciphered. Cation chloride cotransporters are involved in
3 cell volume and osmolarity under the post translational control of the WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 kinases
4 that sense these cell modifications. WNKs stimulate SPAK-OSR1 which directly phosphorylates
5 CCC, stimulating the NKCCs and inhibiting the KCCs resulting in chloride influx.³³ This pathway
6 is deregulated in several neurological disorders (autism, schizophrenia, hydrocephalus),⁵⁶ and
7 particularly in neuropathic pain where WNK1 dependent high chloride level in the dorsal horn
8 result in a default of GABA inhibition.³⁴ Here, we show for the first time in human MCDs such a
9 deregulation of NKCC1 and KCC2 expression levels, as specific inhibition⁵² of WNK1/SPAK-
10 OSR1 with N EthylMaleimide and staurosporine restores a high KCC2/NKCC1 ratio and blocks
11 epileptic activities.

12 In the context of mTORpathies, we then investigated a possible link between mTOR and
13 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 at the post translational level. Indeed, AKT directly phosphorylates WNK1,
14 indirectly phosphorylates WNK3-4,³⁵ and a physical interaction between the mSIN1 subunit of
15 mTORC2 and SPAK-OSR1 was found in Hela cells, and between mSIN1 and WNK1 in the kidney.
16^{36,57} Here we confirm in human pediatric MCD through co immunoprecipitation assays, that
17 endogenous mTOR and mSIN1 interact with WNK1, and that mSIN1 interacts with SPAK-OSR1.
18 The presence of these physical interactions led us to explore whether the hyperactivation of the
19 mTOR pathway was involved in phosphorylation level changes of KCC2 and NKCC1. While
20 blocking this signaling at different levels with BYL 719, Everolimus and rapamycin, we could
21 show decreased phosphorylation of Ser³⁷³ in SPAK-OSR and Thr⁹⁰⁶ KCC2. Both Everolimus and
22 Rapamycin reduced phosphorylation of Thr^{203,207,212} of NKCC1 in MCD slices, while BYL719
23 didn't significantly affect this level maybe because it was acting upstream the mutated MTOR. We
24 further demonstrate that kinase dependent phosphorylation interactions between mTOR /
25 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 /NKCC1/KCC2 lead to a modification of the membranous KCC2/NKCC1
26 ratio, while decreased phosphorylation of mSIN1 by rapamycin resulted in a decrease
27 mSIN1/WNK1 and mSIN1/SPAK-OSR1 interaction. We showed with biotinylation approaches
28 that the phosphorylation level of C-terminal Thr⁹⁰⁶ is a key determinant of KCC2 subcellular
29 localization at the membrane. mTOR pathway activation contributes therefore to KCC2
30 membranous declustering through phosphorylation cascades.

1 As KCC2 down regulation leads to a depolarizing shift of E_{Cl^-} and GABA depolarization in the
2 subiculum in hippocampal sclerosis, ⁵⁸ we eventually studied chloride conductance of MCD
3 membranes using xenopus oocytes. Two electrodes voltage clamp then showed that GABA
4 exposure led to depolarization, confirming previously published data of the paradoxically
5 depolarizing neuronal effect of GABA in MCDs, at the network level on human cortical slices, ^{22,32}
6 and at the single cell level. ^{23,59}. Inhibition of MTOR pathway with Rapamycin treatment restored
7 E_{GABA} on xenopus oocytes by inhibiting chloride accumulation, and suppressed epileptiform
8 activity on the patient's MCD slices ex vivo, in line with anti-epileptic effects reported in
9 randomized controlled trials of children with TSC treated with Everolimus. ^{60,61} Furthermore, a
10 time frequency analysis revealed a pattern of rhythmic oscillations, potentially involved in epileptic
11 activity spreading, reduced by rapamycin application, suggesting an active effect of the drug in
12 controlling epileptic propagation.

13 Altogether, our data highlight one of the possible mechanisms of neuronal hyperexcitability in
14 MCDs, while mTOR hyperactivation leads to GABA depolarization. This pathway can be targeted
15 at multiple levels, paving the way for adjunctive specific antiepileptic drugs in Focal Cortical
16 Dysplasia.

18 **Data availability**

19 Data supporting the findings of this study are available on request from study authors.

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7

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13

14 **Competing interests**

15 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

16

17 **Supplementary material**

18 Supplementary material is available at *Brain* online.

19

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6 **Figure legends**

7
8 **Figure 1 Methodological illustration of the study.** *A/* presurgical evaluation. Imaging of a patient
9 with a FCD located in vicinity of the circular sulcus of the right insular lobe. Red arrow displays
10 the FCD with increased intensity on FLAIR sagittal MRI (top left) and ^{18}F -FDG PET
11 hypometabolism (bottom left). Intracranial EEG recordings were performed with stereo EEG (T1
12 weighted MRI, top right) allowing focal resection (post operative T1 weighted MRI bottom right).
13 Epileptic interictal activity was restricted to the proximal plots of the electrodes Q-R-X, and typical
14 of this patient consisted of synchronizing pattern localized in the abnormal sulcus and anterior short
15 insular gyrus. *B/* (a) Cortical dysplasia is ablated with subpial “en bloc” resection, transferred to
16 the lab in oxygenated sucrose based aACSF, and the tissue is then cut in 400 μm thick slices. *C /*
17 Electrophysiology study was performed with a 10 x 12 multielectrode array that allows extensive
18 mapping of spontaneous epileptic activity in artificial oxygenated aACSF or under
19 pharmacological modulation in the bathing solution. Membrane preparation and micro-
20 transplantation into *Xenopus* oocytes allows to study GABA induced currents and E_{GABA} . *D/*
21 Expression studies allow to analyze chloride cotransporters expression in basal conditions and after
22 pharmacological modulation, both with immunohistochemistry, immunofluorescence, and Western
23 blot analysis.

24
25 **Figure 2 Characteristics of FCD cortical samples.** *A/* Hematoxylin phloxin safron (HPS)
26 staining and immunostaining of a surgical specimen displaying a focal cortical dysplasia type II
27 with loss of cortical cytoarchitecture (Anti-NeuN immunostaining, scale bar = 50 μm) and the
28 presence of cytomegalic neurons with densified Nissl corpus (HPS and anti-MAP2
29 immunostaining, scale bars = 100 μm) and a strong pS6 cytoplasmic expression (anti-pS6, scale
30 bar 100 μm). Scale bars in a = 500 μm . Dysmorphic neurons and balloon cells in focal cortical

1 dysplasia type IIb. Scale bars = 100 μ M. Western blotting for pS6 in brain tissues from subjects
 2 with FCD type IIb and controls shows increased expression level of pS6 protein in brain tissues of
 3 FCD type II compared to controls. Densitometric analysis of the pS6 bands were quantified to
 4 GAPDH for each experimental condition. ($n = 5$ WB, $N = 3$ MCD: 2FCD and 1TSC and 3 controls:
 5 Stroke / Rasmussen / Peritumoral Cortex). **B.** Genomic analysis of the cohort shows mutations in
 6 the PI3K/AKT/MTOR with NGS identified somatic mutation in half of the cases with a low VAF.
 7 **C/**MEA recordings of patient's cortical slices ex vivo display spontaneous interictal discharges in
 8 physiological artificial cerebrospinal fluid in vitro. The box plots illustrate the characteristics of the
 9 local field potentials in the MCD cohort. **D/**KCC2 expression levels are reduced in all FCD II
 10 patients compared to controls. Brains slices lysates from control, and MCD were probed for KCC2
 11 and NKCC1 levels. KCC2 and NKCC1 expressions were normalized to GAPDH. Nine independent
 12 Western blot analyses are shown from $N = 3$ controls (Stroke / Rasmussen / Peritumoral Cortex)
 13 and $N = 6$ MCD patients FCD (2FCD, 2TSC and 2HMG). Reduced KCC2 expression levels are
 14 found in MCDs (0.199 ± 0.032 vs 1.281 ± 0.070 ; P value = <0.001). NKCC1 expression levels are
 15 increased in MCDs (1.253 ± 0.072 vs 0.674 ± 0.054 ; P value = <0.001). The KCC2/NKCC1 ratio
 16 is significantly reduced in FCDII compared to controls (1.253 ± 0.072 vs 0.674 ± 0.054 ; P value =
 17 $<0,001$). **E/** Immunohistochemistry analysis and cell counting show reduced membranous
 18 expression of KCC2 in the MTOR group. Hematoxylin phloxin safron (HPS) and anti-KCC2
 19 immunostaining from a pseudo control (upper panel, scale bar = 100 μ m) and a MTOR patient
 20 (lower panel, scale bar = 100 μ m) illustrating membranous expression of KCC2 (Mb) in pseudo-
 21 control group (Ctl) and intracytoplasmic accumulation of KCC2 (IC KCC2) in MTOR patients that
 22 was confirmed by cell counting.

23
 24 **Figure 3** *WNK1/SPAK-OSR1* regulate chloride co transporter expression in FCD. **A/**NEM and
 25 Staurosporine impair WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 phosphorylation *Top*, Representative Western blots and
 26 quantification of SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³ expression levels of Brains slices lysates under DMSO, N
 27 EthylMalmeide and Staurosporine. Bottom, SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³ expression was normalized to total
 28 SPAK-OSR1 ($n = 4$ and $N = 3$ MCD patients: 2FCD and 1HMG). SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³/total SPAK-
 29 OSR1 ratio was lower ($P <0.001$) in NEM (0.494 ± 0.025) and staurosporine (0.415 ± 0.025)
 30 conditions than in DMSO (1.036 ± 0.016). **B/** NEM and Staurosporine treatment increases KCC2
 31 expression and restores KCC2/NKCC1 ratio. Top: Representative Western blot from Brains slices

1 lysates from DMSO-treated, NEM-treated and staurosporine-treated were probed for KCC2 and
2 NKCC1 levels. Bottom: NEM and staurosporine restore KCC2/NKCC1 ratio. KCC2 and NKCC1
3 expressions were normalized to GAPDH ($n = 4$ and $N = 4$ patients 2FCD, 1HMG and 1TSC). Error
4 bars represent S.E. Band intensities were quantified using ImageJ software. *C/* Inhibition of
5 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 by NEM decreases epileptic activities in vitro. Representative recordings in
6 a single electrode of spontaneous interictal activity recorded in cortical FCD patient in vitro before
7 (aACSF), during 0.5mM NEM treatment and after washout with aACSF. NEM inhibited the
8 spontaneous seizure on brains human slices MCD.

9
10 **Figure 4 phosphorylation cascades underlying mTOR and CCC interactions.** *A/* MTOR and
11 WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 have a direct physical interaction that is inhibited by Rapamycin. *Left panel:*
12 WNK1 protein was immunoprecipitated with an anti-wnk1 antibody, the immuno precipitate was
13 further probed with anti-mTOR antibody to detect mTOR on Western blot. *Middle panel:* Brain
14 slice were pretreated with DMSO, rapamycin or WNK463 inhibitor for 30 min before lysis. The
15 lysat was immunoprecipitated with an antibody directed against mSIN1 and analyzed by western
16 blot with anti-wnk1. *Right panel:* Brain slices were pretreated with DMSO or rapamycin for 30
17 min before lysis. The protein interaction of SPAK/OSR and mSIN1 was assessed by co-
18 immunoprecipitation. *B/* Inhibition of mTOR dephosphorylates WNK1/SPAK-OSR1 and chloride
19 cotransporters. *Left panels.* Immunoblots for evaluating changes in SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³ expression.
20 GAPDH was used as a loading control. ($n = 4$ and $N = 4$ MCD patients: 2FCD, 1HMG and 1TSC).
21 SPAK-OSR1pS³⁷³/total SPAK-OSR1 ratio was lower in BYL719, Everolimus and Rapamycin
22 conditions than in DMSO. Error bars represent S.E. *Middle and right panels.* Quantitative analyses
23 of KCC2 pThr⁹⁰⁶ and NKCC1pTh^{203,207,212} upon BYL719, Everolimus and Rapamycin treatment
24 in brain slices neurons ($n = 6 - 4$ western blot respectively and 4 patients:2FCD, 1HMG and 1TSC).
25 Slices were treated with DMSO (control),10 μ M BYL719, 1 μ M Everolimus, or 0.5 μ M
26 Rapamycin, respectively, for 30 min. Immunoprecipitated KCC2 and NKCC1 were probed for
27 KCC2pThr⁹⁰⁶ and NKCC1pTh^{203,207,212}. Densitometric analysis of the KCC2pThr⁹⁰⁶ and
28 NKCC1pTh^{203,207,212} bands were performed after normalization to total KCC2 and total NKCC1
29 for each experimental condition. *C/* mTOR inhibition restoresKCC2/NKCC1 ratio. Representative
30 Western blot of proteins of slice lysates (left panel) probed with KCC2, KCC1 and GAPDH
31 antibodies. Densitometric analysis of the KCC2 and NKCC1 bands were quantified to GAPDH for

1 each experimental condition ($n = 6$ Western blot and $N = 5$ patients: 2FCD, 2HMH and 1TSC). Bar
 2 graph shows relative levels of KCC2/GAPDH, NKCC1/GAPDH and KCC2/NKCC1 ratio.

3
 4 **Figure 5 mTOR inhibition restores KCC2 membrane insertion.** A/ Quantification of
 5 membranous KCC2. Brain slices were pretreated with vehicle (DMSO) or rapamycin for 30 min
 6 before lysis. Slices were then labeled with biotinylation reagent. Biotinylated surface proteins were
 7 then separated by streptavidin resin. *Left panel.* Representative Western blot of total, cytosolic and
 8 Biotinylated surface proteins of slice lysates were probed with GAPDH and KCC2 antibodies.
 9 *Right panel.* Bar graph shows relative levels of KCC2/GAPDH in total and cytosolic proteins ($N =$
 10 2 MCD patients and $n = 6$ Western blot). Densitometric analysis of the biotinylated KCC2 band
 11 was performed after normalization for the intracellular amount of KCC2 for each experimental
 12 condition. **B and C/** Subcellular KCC2 repartition Immunofluorescence imaging of FCD in basal
 13 conditions (B, left panel, black rectangle) and after mTOR inhibition (C, right panel, red rectangle)
 14 in 2 different slices. Neuronal (NeuN) KCC2 in pS6+ cells is located in the cytoplasm in FCD, and
 15 on the membrane after rapamycin treatment.

16
 17 **Figure 6 mTOR inhibition restores E_{GABA} and blocks spontaneous IID ex vivo.** A/ GABA
 18 induced current. *Left panel.* GABA induced current (250 μ M of GABA added in ND96) was
 19 measured at holding potential (HP) of -50mV in oocytes incorporating membrane from FCD patient
 20 ($n = 15$ oocytes, $N = 3$ frogs and 3 Patients: 2FCD and 1HMG). Oocytes injected with water were
 21 used as control oocytes. Original tracings showing the current induced by the addition of 250 μ M
 22 GABA in the superfusing medium. *Right panel.* Histograms of the experiments display the effect
 23 of 250 μ M in both types of oocytes. **B/** E_{GABA} depolarization *Left panel.* Current-voltage (I/V)
 24 relationship from oocytes injected with membranes of human brain FCD under ND96 (black),
 25 GABA (red) and GABA+rapamycin (green). The points represent means \pm SE of peak GABA
 26 currents. E_{GABA} was determined as the intercept of the I/V curve with the x axis: E_{GABA} $16.28 \pm$
 27 0.59 mV; E_{GABA} shifts to -29.5 ± 10.24 mV after rapamycin treatment ($P = 0.007$, paired t test; $n =$
 28 14 oocytes, $N = 3$ frogs and $N = 3$ Patients: 2FCD and 1HMG). *Right panel.* Histogram illustrating
 29 the mean \pm SE of E_{rev} oocytes under ND96 (black), GABA (red) and GABA+ rapamycin. (green).
 30 Note that the mean E_{GABA} was significantly more positive in FCD tissues before rapamycin
 31 treatment. Rapamycin application shifts E_{GABA} to more negative potential. Data represented are

1 pooled from 3 separate experiments, with four to five oocytes per experiment ($N=3$ frogs, and 3
2 MCDs, $n = 14$ oocytes). **C/** Rapamycin inhibits spontaneous interictal discharges in FCD slices ex
3 vivo. Representative LFP recordings from a single channel during MEA recordings before
4 pharmacological modulation in aACSF, under Rapamycin ($0.5\mu\text{M}$) treatment, and after washout
5 with aACSF. **D/** Heatmap examples for the 2 – 40 Hz frequency range, for aACSF, Rapamycin and
6 Washed. The heatmaps illustrate the frequency topographic distribution of the data (time window
7 = 10 minutes), according to the IID on the 120 contacts of the MEA grid. The heatmaps use one
8 average value ($\text{Log}_{10}(\text{Pow.})$) for each electrode, using interpolation to calculate and plot values
9 between the electrodes. The red square indicates an active electrode that is further illustrated below.
10 In aACSF, a power distribution pattern, potentially associated with spreading, can be observed.
11 This pattern is suppressed in Rapamycin but reactivated after aACSF washout. Time-resolved
12 superlet spectra for the active electrode reveal Rapamycin suppression and Washed power
13 reactivation. **E/** Bar plots for all the active electrodes spectral power averages (\log_{10}), for aACSF,
14 Rapamycin and Washout. The bars represent continuous series of averages over a 10-minute
15 interval. Error bars = s.e.m. $**=P<0.0$.

16

Figure 1
204x263 mm (DPI)

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Figure 2
207x290 mm (DPI)

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Figure 3
205x173 mm (DPI)

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Figure 4
210x201 mm (DPI)

1
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A

B

Untreated

C

Rapamycin

Figure 5
200x168 mm (DPI)

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Figure 6
210x294 mm (DPI)

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